

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

SYSTEMIC CONNECTIVE TISSUE DISEASES AND RAYNAUD'S PHENOMENON

Bukach O.,

*Bukovyna State Medical University,
assistant of the department of internal medicine*

Tkachuk A.,

Tereshkova V.,

Skutelnyk K.,

Makoviichuk M.

Abstract

Systemic connective tissue diseases are a large group of autoimmune pathologies that affect not only the connective tissue itself, but also internal organs, blood vessels, skin, and joints. They are characterized by a chronic course, multisystem involvement, and difficulty in diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: Raynaud's syndrome, Sjögren's syndrome, autoimmune connective tissue diseases, systemic lupus erythematosus, systemic scleroderma.

Connective tissue performs supporting, protective, and trophic functions. It consists of cells and intercellular substance and is present in the skin, bones, cartilage, tendons, blood vessels, heart, kidneys, and other organs [6].

Major systemic diseases [8]

1. Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). An autoimmune disease in which the immune system attacks its own tissues. Affects the skin, joints, kidneys, brain, and heart.

2. Rheumatoid arthritis (RA). An inflammatory disease that primarily affects the joints, with gradual deformity and loss of function.

3. Systemic scleroderma. Caused by excessive collagen accumulation, leading to fibrosis of the skin and internal organs.

4. Polymyositis and dermatomyositis. Inflammation of muscle tissue with possible involvement of the skin and internal organs.

5. Sjögren's syndrome. Exocrine gland disease, causing dryness of the mucous membranes (eyes, mouth) and systemic manifestations.

The exact etiology of connective tissue diseases is unknown, but the following play a key role [1]:

- Genetic predisposition
- Immune dysregulation
- Viral infections (e.g. EBV)
- Stress factors and hormonal changes

The main clinical manifestations of these diseases [18]

- Fever, fatigue, weight loss
- Joint and muscle pain
- Skin rashes, skin discoloration (Raynaud's syndrome)
- Damage to the heart, kidneys, lungs, and nervous system.

Raynaud's phenomenon or syndrome is a fairly common manifestation in patients with systemic connective tissue diseases. Although this syndrome was described more than 100 years ago, the problems of its pathogenesis, clinical significance, and therapy still need to be resolved. The modern clinician is faced with an ever-growing list of questions about the etiological

and pathogenetic nature of Raynaud's phenomenon, given the obvious heterogeneity of its pathophysiological mechanisms, as well as clinical relevance and, as a consequence, therapeutic approaches. The frequency of Raynaud's syndrome, according to most studies, reaches 5-10%, but no special epidemiological studies have been conducted. Patients with severe Raynaud's syndrome are treated by doctors of various specialties - surgeons, vascular surgeons, internists, neurologists, pediatricians, rheumatologists, and patients with mild forms very often remain outside the medical attention. This suggests that the true prevalence of Raynaud's syndrome is higher [7].

Raynaud's syndrome can be primary or secondary. The diagnostic criteria for primary Raynaud's syndrome include [10]:

- Episodes of vasospasm under the influence of cold or emotional stress.
- Symmetry of attacks.
- Absence of necrosis, ulcers or gangrene.
- Absence of anamnestic data and objective signs of secondary Raynaud's syndrome.
- Normal nail bed capillaries.
- Normal ESR values.
- Negative ANA test results.

Diagnostic criteria for secondary Raynaud's syndrome include [13]:

- Age of onset greater than 30 years.
- Episodes of vasospasm are accompanied by pain, are asymmetric, or are associated with ischemic skin lesions.
- Clinical signs characteristic of connective tissue diseases.
- Detection of specific autoantibodies.
- Signs of microvascular damage during nail bed capillaroscopy.

Raynaud's phenomenon occurs in approximately 3-4% of the adult population, predominantly women [15].

The incidence of Raynaud's phenomenon varies considerably depending on climate, lifestyle (indoor or outdoor activities), and ethnicity.

Many people with the primary form never seek medical attention. They know they tend to have “cold hands” and do not consider it unusual or serious enough to seek medical attention [1].

Raynaud's syndrome should be suspected when there are complaints of discoloration of the fingers or discomfort when exposed to cold.

Vasoconstriction of the digital arteries, arterioles, and arteriovenous shunts causes initial pallor [1].

During this time, deoxygenated blood accumulates, causing cyanosis.

Subsequently, reactive vasodilation of the skin vessels occurs. This, in turn, causes flushing due to rapid blood resaturation [19].

Accordingly, the stages are distinguished [2]:

- Angiospastic.
- Angioparalytic.
- Trophic disorders.

Quite often, patients report only one or two color changes. Do not be particularly concerned that a color is missing, as any color change in response to cold is an important indication of Raynaud's phenomenon. Paresthesia, numbness of the fingers, or a feeling of discomfort are often part of the clinical picture. These symptoms, which are caused, just like the color changes, by tissue ischemia and warming, add to the confidence that you are dealing with Raynaud's phenomenon [14].

The fingers are more commonly involved than the toes. In severe cases, the ears, nose, and tongue are also involved, but this is not typical of primary Raynaud's phenomenon [7].

The attack lasts a few minutes, and is relieved more quickly by warming up. More severe attacks can last for hours, although this is rare, especially in primary Raynaud's phenomenon [22].

Both the ambient temperature and the rate of heat loss are important for an attack to occur. It is not necessary to be in the cold to have an episode of Raynaud's phenomenon. On a summer day, an attack can occur when a person enters a room with air conditioning or when there is a breeze. In severe cases, attacks can occur even at normal temperatures [3].

To recognize Raynaud's syndrome, a history is sufficient. You don't need to witness an attack. There is no need for provocation tests, and besides, they require time, special equipment, and are not sensitive and specific enough [4].

If your patient reports only one discoloration of the fingers or toes or complains of paresthesias or numbness in response to cold, you can diagnose probable Raynaud's phenomenon. If repeated episodes of biphasic or triphasic color changes occur, both in response to cold and under normal conditions, this is sufficient to arrive at a definitive diagnosis. All of these manifestations of the disease are typical in severe cases [16].

Diagnosing Raynaud's syndrome is fairly easy. It is much more difficult to determine the form of the disease (primary or secondary). Rheumatologists study the full history of the disease, conduct an examination, and prescribe additional tests. Diagnostics may include [17]:

- Blood test (including both a complete blood count and the determination of specific antibodies in case of suspicion of a systemic connective tissue disease);

- Capillaroscopy (examination of the vessels of the fingers).

Once the diagnosis is established, it is necessary to decide whether the phenomenon is primary or secondary.

Primary Raynaud's phenomenon (Raynaud's disease) has no specific cause or underlying disease. It usually occurs in young, healthy women after they have started menstruating and after the age of 20. Symptoms may disappear after menopause. Episodes of the disease are in most cases mild, symmetrical, involving all fingers, sometimes toes. There are no ulcers on the fingers. Normal microscopic picture of the nail bed capillaries [5].

Secondary Raynaud's phenomenon (Raynaud's syndrome) occurs as a manifestation of another disease. The secondary nature of Raynaud's phenomenon should be suspected in all men, in all prepubertal girls, in women in whom it occurs after the age of 35, in any patient, regardless of age and gender, if he has other symptoms of systemic connective tissue disease, as well as in all patients with such serious manifestations that they interfere with leading a normal lifestyle [3].

It can be assumed that the attacks are caused by secondary Raynaud's phenomenon in cases where ulcers have appeared on the fingers. If only a few fingers are involved in the process or if the attacks occur asymmetrically, then in such cases the Raynaud's phenomenon is caused by an organic vascular pathology.

What diseases cause secondary Raynaud's phenomenon [12]:

- Autoimmune connective tissue diseases (dermatomyositis, rheumatoid arthritis, Sjögren's syndrome, systemic lupus erythematosus, systemic scleroderma, vasculitis).

- Professional activities related to working with vibrating tools.

- Neurological and vascular diseases (atherosclerosis, carpal tunnel syndrome, crutch pressure, diabetes, embolism, chest exit syndrome, thromboangiitis obliterans, thrombosis).

- Hematological disorders (cold agglutinin disease, cryoglobulinemia, leukemia, paraproteinemia, erythremia, thrombocytosis).

- Drugs and toxins (beta-blockers, bleomycin, vinblastine, cisplatin, ergotamine preparations, narcotics, polyvinyl chloride).

- Other pathological conditions (anorexia, atypical angina, fibromyalgia, hypothyroidism, malignant tumors, migraine, primary pulmonary hypertension).

Depending on whether the patient has primary or secondary Raynaud's phenomenon, the treatment will depend.

In cases of primary Raynaud's phenomenon, in which no tissue damage occurs, symptomatic treatment is the priority. Explanation, preventive measures, and conservative therapy are sufficient. Advise the patient to dress warmly, wear a hat and gloves in cold weather.

Situations and medications that trigger attacks should be avoided, and smokers should quit [9].

If these measures do not provide sufficient symptomatic improvement, try calcium channel blockers. Nifedipine is particularly helpful. Other calcium channel blockers, such as diltiazem, can also be used, but their effectiveness is less pronounced. Long-acting forms may be prescribed for convenience. The usual dose is 30-90 mg/day, but sometimes 120 mg/day is needed [23].

Calcium channel blockers. These medications relax blood vessels, reducing the frequency and severity of attacks in most people with Raynaud's. These drugs may also help with ulcers. Examples of drugs include nifedipine, amlodipine, and felodipine.

Alpha-blockers. Some people may be prescribed other medications called alpha-blockers, which counteract norepinephrine, a hormone that constricts blood vessels. Examples of medications include prazosin and doxazosin [21].

Vasodilators. Nitroglycerin cream applied to the base of the fingers may help skin ulcers heal. Some vasodilators are widely used to treat other conditions, including the following drugs: losartan, sildenafil, antidepressants (fluoxetine), and prostaglandins [22].

Patients with Raynaud's phenomenon are advised to quit smoking, avoid vasoconstrictive medications (beta-blockers, ergotamines), and avoid cold and sudden changes in temperature. Dress warmly in cold weather and wear a hat. It is better to wear gloves with one separate finger than with five fingers. Use a hand warmer. Apply nifedipine and nitroglycerin ointment [20].

ACE inhibitors, like pentoxifylline, are not particularly helpful in this disease.

If there are ulcers, they must be clean, protected from contamination with antimicrobial dressings, and promptly cleaned of necrotic particles [11].

Conclusion

Raynaud's phenomenon in systemic connective tissue diseases requires an interdisciplinary approach, early diagnosis and long-term follow-up. It is important to raise awareness both among doctors and without help, because timely treatment allows to preserve the quality of life.

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